

Original Article

Workload Pressure and Health Status of Working Women at Higher Education Institutions in Pakistan

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Abstract

This study has been designed to examine the workload pressure and health status of working women at the university level. Women are working under pressure, and it negatively results in their health status. This study uses a quantitative approach, and a survey has been conducted. A sample of 754 women has been drawn from four (two public and two private sectors) universities in the Punjab province, Pakistan using a proportionate random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire has been administered by the researcher to collect information from the respondents. It uses an attitudinal scale of (dis)agreement and pilot testing has also been done on 30 working women to check the reliability of the instrument. Statistical analysis has been made to draw results and conclusions. The study findings reveal that heavy workload, decision making issues, and responsiveness issues among working women has been directly affecting the health status at tertiary-level educational institutions. Correspondingly, heavy workload, decision making, and responsiveness issues has an indirect effect on the health status of working women at the tertiary level of educational institutions.

Keywords: Workload Pressure, Health Status, Working Women, Decision Making, Higher Education

Introduction

It has been observed that several issues of workload faced by working women at the university (Aisoli-Orake et al., 2022; Kasbuntoro, Maemunah, Mahfud, Fahlevi, & Parashakti, 2020; Zahid, Hooley, & Neary, 2020). There has been a contrast in the assignment of workload in developed and developing countries (Jaaskelainen, López-Iniguez, & Phillips, 2020; Shoaib, Zaman, & Abbas, 2024; Tara & Ahsan, 2020; Ull-ann Javaid, Khan, & Siddiq, 2020). In developed countries, the workload is assigned according to the job description and status of the university (Griffith & Altinay, 2020; Hamid et al., 2020; Shoaib, Shehzadi, & Abbas, 2024). There is always a defined criterion of workload among the university working women (A. Ahmad, 2020; Arcarons, 2020; Shoaib, Ali, & Abbas, 2024; Yang & Choo, 2019). According to the designation of the working women, the workload is assigned and thus, workload policies are implemented (Kersh, 2018; Loureiro, 2019). In developed countries, there are clearer policies regarding academic and administrative workforce that are implemented in the same manner (Anjum & Muazzam, 2018). Similarly, developed countries have sufficient infrastructure and staffing to execute the plan of action for academic activities (Coate & Howson, 2016; Erdamar & Demirel, 2014; Graham, 2015). Here, women academicians are supposed to carry out academic activities as per the required workload (Dobebe, Rundle-Thiele, & Kopanidis, 2014; Griffith & Altinay, 2020; Tower, Lazzari, Faul, & Alvarez, 2015). However, the situation in developing countries is different from that of developed countries (Ali, 2018; Kersh, 2018).

Review of Literature

Research shows many issues of workload faced by university teachers (Ali, 2018; Anjum & Muazzam, 2018). There has been a contrast in the assignment of workload in developed and developing countries (Arcarons, 2020;

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Arif, Naveed, & Aslam, 2017). In developed countries, the workload is assigned according to the job description and status of the university (Dobele et al., 2014; Erdamar & Demirel, 2014). There is always a defined criterion of workload among the teachers (Coate & Howson, 2016). According to the designation of the teacher, the workload is assigned and thus, workload policies are implemented (Griffith & Altinay, 2020). In developed countries, there are clearer policies regarding academic and administrative workforce that are implemented in the same manner (Jaaskelainen et al., 2020). Similarly, developed countries have sufficient infrastructure and staffing to execute the plan of action for academic activities (Melin, Astvik, & Bernhard-Oettel, 2014). Here, women academicians are supposed to carry out academic activities as per the required workload (Papanek, 1973; Shoaib & Ullah, 2021a). However, the situation in developing countries is different from that of developed countries (Miller, 1984; Qureshi et al., 2013; Rehman & Azam Roomi, 2012; Shoaib & Ullah, 2021b).

Research shows that higher education in most developing countries lacks infrastructure (Arif et al., 2017; Asad & Najam, 2015). These studies stated that a larger operation cannot be executed without proper infrastructure (Anjum & Muazzam, 2018; Shoaib & Ullah, 2019). The majority of developing countries lack infrastructure (Fatima & Sahibzada, 2012; Hamid et al., 2020; Hashmi, Khurshid, & Hassan, 2007). Similarly, higher education institutions lack proper staffing (Ayub & Rafif, 2011). This shows that educational programs are initiated without proper policies of staffing (Malik, Saif, Gomez, Khan, & Hussain, 2010; Shoaib, Mehmood, & Butt, 2022). It is noted that women academicians are taken on a contingent base and they are mainly not trained to teach (Noor & Zainuddin, 2011). On the other hand, the recruitment of teaching staff is also less for teaching (Nadeem & Abbas, 2009; Shoaib, 2023; Shoaib, Latif, & Usmani, 2013). Besides, the teaching staff is assigned administrative responsibilities that affect their teaching practices (Khurshid, Parveen, & Yousuf, 2014). In addition, teaching staff already in low numbers are assigned extra workloads that further worsen their teaching skills and thus they are unable to focus on teaching properly (Abdullah, Usmani, & Shoaib, 2023; Hussain, 2009; Kausar, Mumta, & Shoaib, 2023). This shows that proper policies are not followed for academic and administrative work in developing countries (Umer & Zia-ur-Rehman, 2013). Consequently, women academicians have to bear more teaching loads (Noor & Zainuddin, 2011). It is thus concluded that heavy workloads affect the teaching capabilities of women academicians in higher education in developing countries (Hamid et al., 2020; Haq, Iqbal, & Rahman, 2008; Hashmi et al., 2007).

The situation of decision-making is differently found in developed and developing countries (Nazneen, Hossain, & Chopra, 2019). In developed countries, there is proper employment of higher education policies that resolve the issues of decision-making at both academic and administrative levels (Erdamar & Demirel, 2014). Research shows that academic and administrative issues are addressed by the proper decision-making policies in developed countries (L. A. Webber, 2017). Both tiers are supposed to take up their duties according to the statuses of the institutions (Yang & Choo, 2019). It is pertinent to mention here that any institution provided with infrastructure and staffing is easier to respond to the academic and administrative goals they have (Erdamar & Demirel, 2014). Similarly, the decision-making issues are settled due to effective policy measures (Khurshid et al., 2014). However, higher education in the majority of developing countries is deficient in decision-making owing to weak policies (Malik et al., 2010). Similarly, the issues of decision-making arise due to several factors identified by Shoaib et al. (2013). They noted that policymaking is weakened primarily. It directly affects decision-making in higher education (Shoaib, Naseer, & Naseer, 2023; L. Webber, 2015). In contrast, some developing countries have a strong foothold of policies in education however decision-making issues always create an uncertain situation (Betz & Neff, 2017; Choo, 2015). It further worsens the administrative and academic decisions and thus a vacuum is created in the execution of decisions by the authorities (Davies, 2008; Shoaib, Ali, & Akbar, 2021). It connotes that poor higher education policies lead to uncertainty in decision making and thus a failure has been found on the shoulders of authorities (Begum-Sadaquat & Sheikh, 2011; Berggren, 2011). To sum up, it is noted that decision-making issues are mainly found in the education system of developing countries (Anwar, Shoaib, & Javed, 2013).

Weak policies create non-responsiveness to the set goals in any sphere including higher education (Haque, 2003). In higher education, proper policy-making lead to the progress of any institution (Davies, 2008; Ha, 2013; Shoaib, Ahmad, Ali, & Abdullah, 2021). Besides, it is the administration of the institutions that respond to the issues and implement the decisions in a proper manner (J. Ahmad, Shoaib, & Shaukat, 2021; Choo, 2015; Dale, 2002). Research shows that responsiveness issues are less likely a problem in higher education in developed countries (Anagol & Grey, 2017; Betz & Neff, 2017; Shoaib & Abdullah, 2021). These studies revealed that effective policies can increase responsiveness and minimize the issues of noncompliance. It is also stated that responsiveness to academic and administrative issues is more likely associated with appropriate policies and

effective decision-making strategies to address the issues they encounter. In contrast, the issues of responsiveness are found in the educational structure including higher education in many developing countries. In Ghana, due to the patriarchal structure of higher education responsiveness issues exist at a large scale (Assarsson, Petersen, Högberg, Strandh, & Johansson, 2018; Herzig, 2010; Makiwane, Ndinda, & Botsis, 2012). A similar situation is found in the majority of African countries (Ilie & Rose, 2018; Makiwane et al., 2012). The following conceptual framework has been developed based on above review of literature;

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework of Model

The

Data and Methods

This article has opted quantitative study approach and the sample size is more than 30. The population in this study has been comprised of women working at higher educational institutions i.e., university level. These women are working at four universities of the Punjab province i.e., 1) Government College University Faisalabad, 2) The Islamia University of Bahawalpur 3) Minhaj University Lahore, and 4) University of Management and Technology, Lahore. This study has been conducted using a proportionate random sampling technique giving equal chance to every element/proportion of the study i.e., administrative and faculty jobs, public and private sector universities. A sample of 754 women working at the tertiary level of educational institutions in the Punjab province has been selected using a proportionate random sampling technique. Sample size determination formula (Yamane, 1967) i.e., $n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$ has been and further sample has been proportionally distributed to each public and private sector university. A survey method has been used to conduct the study on working women at the university. A structured questionnaire has been used to collect information and pre-tested from 30 randomly selected women. Further, the normality of data has been checked and Kendall's tau_b and SEM Model has been used to draw conclusion.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 provides Kendall's tau_b test of the variables used in the present study. It has been revealed that there is a weak positive correlation between a heavy workload and decision-making issues, responsiveness issues, familial responsibilities, and the attitude of co-workers among women working at the university. However, a moderate positive correlation has been reported between a heavy workload and dealing issues and health status issues among working women in the university. Similarly, decision-making issues have a positive moderate correlation with responsiveness issues, familial responsibilities, dealing issues, and health status issues among working women at the tertiary level. Contrary, there has been a weak positive correlation between decision-making issues and the attitude of co-workers. To sum up the findings of the table, there is a weak and moderate positive correlation between all the variables i.e., heavy workload, decision-making issues, responsiveness issues, familial responsibilities, the attitude of co-workers, dealing issues, and health status issues among working women at the university level.

Table 1

Kendall's tau_b between Independent Variables and Health Status Issues

Var.	HEWO	DEMI	REIS	FARE	AOCW	DEIS	HESI
HEWO	1.000	.322**	.203**	.239**	.185**	.350**	.456**
DEMI		1.000	.428**	.490**	.249**	.540**	.431**
REIS			1.000	.301**	.265**	.377**	.349**
FARE				1.000	.268**	.399**	.322**
AOCW					1.000	.448**	.335**
DEIS						1.000	.485**
HESI							1.000

Table 2 shows the correlation test of dependent sub-variables with health status issues among working women. Data reflect that there is a moderate positive correlation between physical health issues, psychological health issues, social well-being issues, spiritual health issues, nutritional diet issues, health risk behaviour, and health status issues among working women at the university. It has also been asserted that there is a moderate positive correlation between psychological health issues, social well-being issues, spiritual health issues, nutritional diet issues, health risk behaviour, and health status issues among working women at tertiary level education. The study also finds that there is a high positive correlation between spiritual health issues and health risk behaviour. Similar results have been reported with health status issues among working women at the university. To conclude the findings of the table, there is a weak and moderate positive correlation between all the variables i.e., physical health issues, psychological health issues, social well-being issues, spiritual health issues, nutritional diet issues, health risk behaviour, and health status issues among working women at the university.

Table 2

Kendall's tau_b between Dependent Variables and Health Status Issues

Var.	PHHI	PSHI	SWBI	SPHI	NUDI	HERB	HESI
PHHI	1.000	.450**	.420**	.511**	.384**	.398**	.633**
PSHI		1.000	.337**	.492**	.324**	.392**	.585**
SWBI			1.000	.357**	.195**	.162**	.454**
SPHI				1.000	.605**	.665**	.776**
NUDI					1.000	.626**	.630**
HERB						1.000	.649**
HESI							1.000

Table 3 describes Kendall's tau_b correlation between workload pressure and health status issues among working women at the tertiary level. The study findings reveal a positive moderate correlation between workload pressure and health status issues among working women at the university. It is stated that women are facing workload pressure at the university that results in affecting their health status in a negative way. Hence, the study findings show that there is a positive moderate correlation between workload pressure and health status issues among working women at the university.

Table 3

Kendall's tau_b between Workload Pressure and Health Status Issues

Variables		Workload Pressure	Health Status Issues
Kendall's tau _b	Workload Pressure	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.
		N	754
	Health Status Issues	Correlation Coefficient	.533**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	754

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

SEM Model: Table 4 provides the direct effects of model as presented in the conceptual framework of model. The study findings show that responsiveness issues (Beta value=.179), decision-making issues (Beta value=.187), and heavy workload (Beta value=.106) among working women directly effecting the attitude of co-workers at tertiary-level educational institutions. Similarly, the results also point out that heavy workload (Beta value=.180), decision-making issues (Beta value=.552), and responsiveness issues (Beta value=.108) directly affect dealing issues at the workplace of the university among working women. The study findings also reveal that dealing with issues (Beta value=.285), heavy workload (Beta value=.396), responsiveness issues (Beta value=.124), decision-making issues (Beta value=.092), the attitude of co-workers (Beta value=.048), and familial responsibilities (Beta value=.063) among working women directly affecting health status issues at tertiary level educational institutions.

Table 4
Direct Effects of Model

Variables			Standardized Regression Weights	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
REIS	--->	AOCW	.179	.254	.059	4.327	***
HEWO	--->	DEIS	.180	.161	.025	6.384	***
DEMI	--->	DEIS	.552	.557	.033	16.735	***
DEMI	--->	AOCW	.187	.270	.063	4.265	***
HEWO	--->	AOCW	.106	.135	.048	2.832	.005
REIS	--->	DEIS	.108	.107	.031	3.455	***
DEIS	--->	HESI	.285	1.217	.152	8.004	***
HEWO	--->	HESI	.396	1.507	.108	13.914	***
REIS	--->	HESI	.124	.522	.131	3.976	***
DEMI	--->	HESI	.092	.398	.164	2.423	.015
AOCW	--->	HESI	.048	.143	.080	1.790	.073
FARE	--->	HESI	.063	.224	.088	2.531	.011
Covariances							
HEWO	<-->	DEMI		4.800	.445	10.781	***
REIS	<-->	DEMI		5.822	.426	13.680	***
REIS	<-->	HEWO		3.240	.433	7.486	***
Variances							
REIS				10.296	.531	19.404	***
HEWO				12.678	.653	19.404	***
DEMI				9.954	.513	19.404	***
e1				17.786	.917	19.404	***
e4				14.566	.751	19.404	***
e2				4.931	.254	19.404	***
e3				85.773	4.420	19.404	***
Model Fit Summary: Chi-square = 654.620, df = 6, P = .000, AGFI=.992, GFI=.907, CLI=.905, RMSEA=.065							

Table 5
Indirect Effects of Model

Indirect Path	Unstandardized Estimate	Lower	Upper	P-Value	Standardized Estimate
DEMI --> DEIS --> HESI	0.678	0.509	0.877	0.001	0.158***
DEMI --> AOCW --> HESI	0.039	0.002	0.101	0.074	0.009+
HEWO --> DEIS --> HESI	0.195	0.132	0.274	0.001	0.051***
HEWO --> AOCW --> HESI	0.019	0.002	0.050	0.069	0.005+
REIS --> DEIS --> HESI	0.130	0.057	0.221	0.005	0.031**
REIS --> AOCW --> HESI	0.036	0.003	0.087	0.072	0.009+

Table 5 describes the indirect effects of model 1 having dependent variable health status issues among working women at tertiary-level educational institutions. The study findings assert that health status issues among working women at university are indirectly affected by decision-making issues through the mediation of dealing issues (0.158***) and the attitude of co-workers (0.009†). Similarly, the study findings declare that health status issues among working women at university are indirectly affected by heavy workload through the mediation of dealing issues (0.051***) and attitude of co-workers (0.005†). Correspondingly, the study findings affirm that health status issues among working women at university are indirectly affected by responsiveness issues through the mediation of dealing issues (0.031**) and the attitude of co-workers (0.009†).

Figure 2
Model Diagram

Conclusion

The study findings conclude that there is a weak and moderate positive correlation between all the variables i.e., physical health issues, psychological health issues, social well-being issues, spiritual health issues, nutritional diet issues, health risk behaviour, and health status issues among working women at the university. The study also concludes based on the primary data that heavy workload, decision making issues, and responsiveness issues among working women has been directly effecting the health status at tertiary-level educational institutions. Similarly, the results also conclude that attitude of co-workers, dealing issues, and familial responsibilities has been directly affect dealing with issues at the workplace of the university among working women. The study also outlines that workload pressure among working women directly effecting familial responsibilities of them in tertiary-level educational institutions. Correspondingly, heavy workload, decision making, and responsiveness issues has an indirect effect on the health status of working women at the tertiary level of educational institutions.

Policy Implication

The study recommends that workload pressure should be minimized for women working at university by minimizing their workload and improving their health status.

References

- Abdullah, F., Usmani, F., & Shoaib, M. (2023). Psychological Aspects of Violence against Women: A Quantitative Analysis. *Qlantic Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(3), 163-172. <https://doi.org/10.55737/qjss.558066961>
- Ahmad, A. (2020). Eating habits and food choices at work of working women in the banking sector in Islamabad, Pakistan. *Rawal Medical Journal*, 45(3), 698-701.
- Ahmad, J., Shoaib, M., & Shaukat, B. (2021). Academic Library Resources and Services at Higher Education Institutions during COVID-19 Pandemic: A Case of Students' Satisfaction. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1-17.
- Aisoli-Orake, R., Bue, V., Aisi, M., Ambelye, I., Betasolo, M., Nuru, T., . . . Roberts, N. (2022). Creating sustainable networks to enhance women's participation in higher education in Papua New Guinea. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 44(2), 208-220. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2022.2037267>
- Ali, T. (2018). Raising teachers' voices: an in-depth qualitative inquiry into teachers' working conditions and professional development needs in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, a province of Pakistan. *Teacher Development*, 22(1), 78-104. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13664530.2017.1308432>
- Anagol, P., & Grey, D. J. R. (2017). Rethinking Gender and Justice in South Asia, 1772–2013. *Cultural and Social History*, 14(4), 419-427. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14780038.2017.1358972>
- Anjum, A., & Muazzam, A. (2018). The Gendered Nature of Workplace Bullying in the Context of Higher Education. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 33, 493-505.
- Anwar, B., Shoaib, M., & Javed, S. (2013). Women's autonomy and their role in decision making at household level: a case of rural Sialkot, Pakistan. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 23(1), 129-136.
- Arcarons, A. F. (2020). The working mother-in-law effect on the labour force participation of first and second-generation immigrant women in the UK. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 46(5), 893-912. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2018.1539268>
- Arif, A., Naveed, S., & Aslam, R. (2017). Factors causing stress among Pakistani working women. *Pakistan Administrative Review*, 1(3), 159-174.
- Asad, S., & Najam, N. (2015). Work status differences related to personality traits and psychological health among professional women. *Pakistan Journal of Psychological Research*, 30(2), 393-405.
- Assarsson, R., Petersen, S., Högberg, B., Strandh, M., & Johansson, K. (2018). Gender inequality and adolescent suicide ideation across Africa, Asia, the South Pacific and Latin America – a cross-sectional study based on the Global School Health Survey (GSHS). *Global Health Action*, 11(sup3), 1663619. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16549716.2019.1663619>
- Ayub, N., & Rafif, S. (2011). The relationship between work motivation and job satisfaction. *Pakistan Business Review*, 13(2), 332-347.
- Begum-Sadaquat, M., & Sheikh, Q. t. a. A. (2011). Employment situation of women in Pakistan. *International journal of social economics*, 38(2), 98-113.
- Berggren, C. (2011). Gender equality policies and higher education careers. *Journal of Education and Work*, 24(1-2), 141-161. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639080.2010.534442>
- Betz, J., & Neff, D. (2017). Social policy diffusion in South Asia. *Journal of Asian Public Policy*, 10(1), 25-39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17516234.2016.1258520>
- Choo, S. S. (2015). Citizenship education in Asia. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 35(2), 149-152. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2015.1048764>
- Coate, K., & Howson, C. K. (2016). Indicators of esteem: gender and prestige in academic work. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 37(4), 567-585. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01425692.2014.955082>
- Dale, A. (2002). Social Exclusion of Pakistani and Bangladeshi Women. *Sociological Research Online*, 7(3), 69-81. doi:10.5153/sro.741
- Davies, L. (2008). Gender, education, extremism and security. *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 38(5), 611-625. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057920802351432>
- Dobele, A. R., Rundle-Thiele, S., & Kopanidis, F. (2014). The cracked glass ceiling: equal work but unequal status. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 33(3), 456-468. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2013.841654>

- Erdamar, G., & Demirel, H. (2014). Investigation of work-family, family-work conflict of the teachers. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 116, 4919-4924.
- Fatima, N., & Sahibzada, S. A. (2012). An empirical analysis of factors affecting work life balance among university teachers: the case of Pakistan. *Journal of International Academic Research*, 12(1), 16-29.
- Graham, A. T. (2015). Academic staff performance and workload in higher education in the UK: the conceptual dichotomy. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 39(5), 665-679. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2014.971110>
- Griffith, A. S., & Altinay, Z. (2020). A framework to assess higher education faculty workload in U.S. universities. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 57(6), 691-700. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2020.1786432>
- Ha, P. L. (2013). Education in South-East Asia. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 43(1), 142-143. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764X.2013.767545>
- Hamid, S., Mureed, S., Kayani, A., Javed, K., Khan, A., Awais, S., . . . Fixsen, D. L. (2020). Learning Active Implementation Frameworks: the role of implementation teams in a case study from Pakistan. *Global Health Action*, 13(1), 1805164. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16549716.2020.1805164>
- Haq, Z., Iqbal, Z., & Rahman, A. (2008). Job stress among community health workers: a multi-method study from Pakistan. *International journal of mental health systems*, 2(1), 1-6.
- Haque, M. S. (2003). Citizen Participation in Governance Through Representation: Issue of Gender in East Asia. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 26(5), 569-590. <https://doi.org/10.1081/PAD-120019236>
- Hashmi, H. A., Khurshid, M., & Hassan, I. (2007). Marital adjustment, stress and depression among working and non-working married women. *Internet journal of medical update*, 2(1), 19-26.
- Herzig, P. (2010). Communal networks and gender: placing identities among South Asians in Kenya. *South Asian Diaspora*, 2(2), 165-184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19438192.2010.491296>
- Hussain, I. (2009). *Problems of working women in Karachi, Pakistan*: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Ilie, S., & Rose, P. (2018). Who benefits from public spending on higher education in South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa? *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 48(4), 630-647. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057925.2017.1347870>
- Jaaskelainen, T., López-Iniguez, G., & Phillips, M. (2020). Music students' experienced workload, livelihoods and stress in higher education in Finland and the United Kingdom. *Music Education Research*, 22(5), 505-526. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14613808.2020.1841134>
- Kasbuntoro, D. I., Maemunah, S., Mahfud, I., Fahlevi, M., & Parashakti, R. D. (2020). Work-life balance and job satisfaction: A case study of employees on banking companies in Jakarta. *International Journal of Control and Automation*, 13(4), 439-451.
- Kausar, N., Mumta, S., & Shoaib, M. (2023). Lived Experiences of Individuals with Gender Dysphoria: A Qualitative Analysis. *Sexuality and Culture*, 1-18.
- Kersh, R. (2018). Women in Higher Education: Exploring Stressful Workplace Factors and Coping Strategies. *NASPA Journal About Women in Higher Education*, 11(1), 56-73. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19407882.2017.1372295>
- Khurshid, S., Parveen, Q., & Yousuf, M. I. (2014). A Comparative Study of Psychological Adjustment of the Children Belonging to Working and Non-working Women in Nuclear and Joint Family System. *The Anthropologist*, 18(2), 583-589. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09720073.2014.11891576>
- Loureiro, M. (2019). Debating empowerment: men's views of women's access to work in public spaces in Pakistan-administered Kashmir. *Contemporary South Asia*, 27(4), 531-548. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09584935.2019.1688254>
- Makiwane, M., Ndinda, C., & Botsis, H. (2012). Gender, race and ageing in South Africa. *Agenda*, 26(4), 15-28. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10130950.2012.755380>
- Malik, M. I., Saif, M. I., Gomez, S. F., Khan, N., & Hussain, S. (2010). Balancing work and family through social support among working women in Pakistan. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(13), 2864-2870.
- Melin, M., Astvik, W., & Bernhard-Oettel, C. (2014). New work demands in higher education. A study of the relationship between excessive workload, coping strategies and subsequent health among academic staff. *Quality in Higher Education*, 20(3), 290-308. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13538322.2014.979547>
- Miller, B. D. (1984). Daughter neglect, women's work, and marriage: Pakistan and Bangladesh compared. *Medical Anthropology*, 8(2), 109-126. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01459740.1984.9965895>

- Nadeem, M. S., & Abbas, Q. (2009). The impact of work life conflict on job satisfactions of employees in Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 4(5), 63-83.
- Nazneen, S., Hossain, N., & Chopra, D. (2019). Introduction: contentious women's empowerment in South Asia. *Contemporary South Asia*, 27(4), 457-470. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09584935.2019.1689922>
- Noor, N. M., & Zainuddin, M. (2011). Emotional labor and burnout among female teachers: Work–family conflict as mediator. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, 14(4), 283-293.
- Papanek, H. (1973). Men, women, and work: Reflections on the two-person career. *American Journal of Sociology*, 78(4), 852-872.
- Qureshi, M. I., Iftikhar, M., Abbas, S. G., Hassan, U., Khan, K., & Zaman, K. (2013). Relationship between job stress, workload, environment and employees turnover intentions: What we know, what should we know. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 23(6), 764-770.
- Rehman, S., & Azam Roomi, M. (2012). Gender and work-life balance: a phenomenological study of women entrepreneurs in Pakistan. *Journal of small business and enterprise development*, 19(2), 209-228.
- Shoaib, M. (2023, September 22). Galvanising Bourdieu's typology with Pakistani education and social class. *The Nation*, p. 4.
- Shoaib, M., & Abdullah, F. (2021). COVID-19 backlash: psycho-social impacts of outbreak in Pakistan. *Health Education*, 121(3), 265-274.
- Shoaib, M., & Ullah, H. (2019). Female and Male Students' Educational Performance in Tertiary Education in the Punjab, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Social Issues*, X(1), 83-100.
- Shoaib, M., & Ullah, H. (2021a). Classroom Environment, Teacher, and Girl Students' Learning Skills. *Education and Urban Society*, 53(9), 1039-1063. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00131245211001908>
- Shoaib, M., & Ullah, H. (2021b). Teachers' perspectives on factors of female students' outperformance and male students' underperformance in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(3), 684-699. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-05-2020-0261>
- Shoaib, M., Ahmad, A., Ali, N., & Abdullah, F. (2021). Trend of Research Visualization of Learning, Classroom, and Class Participation in Higher Education Institutions: A Bibliometric Analysis from 2001 to 2020. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 5743, 1-26.
- Shoaib, M., Ali, R., & Akbar, A. (2021). Library Services and Facilities in Higher Education Institutions in Pakistan: Satisfaction of Patrons. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1-19.
- Shoaib, M., Ali, S. R., & Abbas, Z. (2024). Self-Fulfilling Prophecy of Learning Skills Among Students in Higher Education. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(7), 164-177.
- Shoaib, M., Latif, B., & Usmani, F. (2013). Economic contribution changes the decision-making of working women; A case of Bhimben District-AJK. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 16(5), 602-606.
- Shoaib, M., Mehmood, S., & Butt, S. M. (2022). Intention to Leave a Job among Public Sector University Teachers: A Case of Work Environment. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 4(2), 370-383.
- Shoaib, M., Naseer, A., & Naseer, N. (2023). Family Pressure, Social Media Influence, and COVID-19 Vaccination Hesitancy among Students at Higher Education in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 2(3), 295-307.
- Shoaib, M., Shehzadi, K., & Abbas, Z. (2024). Inclusivity, Teacher Competency, and Learning Environment at Higher Education: Empirical Evidences. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(5), 244-261.
- Shoaib, M., Zaman, M. A., & Abbas, Z. (2024). Trends of Research Visualization of Gender Based Violence (GBV) from 1971-2020: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Pakistan Journal of Law, Analysis and Wisdom*, 3(7), 203-216.
- Tara, U., & Ahsan, S. (2020). Cognitive hardiness as a moderator in the relationship between generalized workplace harassment and anger among working women in Pakistan. *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, 30(8), 971-988. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10911359.2020.1781016>
- Tower, L. E., Lazzari, M. M., Faul, A. C., & Alvarez, A. R. (2015). Challenges, Changes, and Impact of the Council on Social Work Education Women's Council: An Update. *Journal of Social Work Education*, 51(4), 702-722. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10437797.2015.1076279>
- Ull-ann Javid, Q., Khan, Z. U., & Siddiq, U. (2020). Societal Challenges faced by Working Women in Pakistan. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(7), 10275-10288.
- Umer, R., & Zia-ur-Rehman, M. (2013). Impact of work life balance and work life conflict on the life satisfaction of working women: A case study of higher education sector of twin cities of Pakistan. *Academic Research International*, 4(5), 445-458.

- Webber, L. (2015). Mature women and higher education: reconstructing identity and family relationships. *Research in Post-Compulsory Education*, 20(2), 208-226. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13596748.2015.1030260>
- Webber, L. A. (2017). Women, higher education and family capital: 'i could not have done it without my family!'. *Research in Post-Compulsory Education*, 22(3), 409-428. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13596748.2017.1358521>
- Yamane, T. (1967). *An Introductory Analysis of Statistics*. In: New York: Harper and Row.
- Yang, H.-M., & Choo, J. (2019). Socioeconomic inequalities in self-rated health: role of work-to-family conflict in married Korean working women. *Women & Health*, 59(8), 921-936. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03630242.2019.1567648>
- Zahid, G., Hooley, T., & Neary, S. (2020). Careers work in higher education in Pakistan: Current practice and options for the future. *British Journal of Guidance & Counselling*, 48(4), 443-453.